

THE HANDLING OF NON-CASH FOOD ASSISTANCE (BPNT) AND ITS EFFECTS ON FOOD RESISTANCE TO BENEFICIARY FAMILIES (KPM) IN 2018-2019 - CASE STUDY: SIANTAR SITALASARI DISTRICT, PEMATANGSIANTAR CITY, INDONESIA

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Abstract:

This study attempts to determine the standard criteria for KPM (beneficiary families) as well as the effect of the BPNT program on increasing household food security and the benefits obtained by kiosks / stalls / shops that work together in the BPNT program. The research method used is descriptive qualitative. KPM or beneficiary families must meet the criteria as a recipient of BPNT by fulfilling 9 variables characteristics of poor households, has experienced the increase in household food security influencing an increase of 35.12% as well as the profits obtained by cooperating stalls / shops earning Rp.1,286,875, - / month net income merely from rice. They also received a reward from BRI bank worth Rp. 2,000 / transaction and purchase of other goods in the Siantar Sitalasari District.

Keywords: poverty criteria, non-cash food aid, beneficiary families, food security

1. Introduction

1.1 Background

The problem of poverty is a social problem that is always relevant to be studied continuously. This is not only because the problem of poverty has existed for a long time, but also because this problem is still present in our midst and even now the symptoms are increasing in line with the crisis that is still faced by Indonesia (Soekanto, 2013; Sjafari, 2014).

One of the problems in efforts to tackle poverty is through data. BPS has two types of data, namely micro and macro, while the type of data used as a reference for

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channeling assistance to the underprivileged people is micro data. Programs on poverty alleviation are started by the government by issuing regulations of President of the Republic of Indonesia Number 15 of 2010, concerning the Acceleration of Poverty Reduction (Zulfaira, 2012).

One program that aims to alleviate poverty is Food Social Assistance, in which whether the community consumes sufficient food. Poverty is closely related to food security issues. Family food security is the ability of the family and all its members at any time to obtain enough food for their activities and healthy life.

According to LIPI in Indriani (2015), there are 4 components that must be met to achieve food security conditions, namely: 1) adequacy of food availability, 2) stability of food availability without fluctuations from season to season or from year to year, 3) accessibility / affordability to food, 4) food quality / safety.

The achievement of good food security at the individual and household level is simultaneously closely related to the food security at the regional level (Indriani, 2015). Revenue is the first factor that affects household food security, both in farm households and non-farmers. Especially for farmers, in addition to selling excess produce to generate income is also expected to be stored as food reserves. Measuring family food security is carried out in stages and measuring it according to the family food security subsystem.

Non-cash food aid is food assistance from the government given to the Beneficiary Families (KPM) every month through an electronic account mechanism or a Combo Card that is used only to buy food at vendors or called *E-warong* in collaboration with the State Bank Association. The benefits of the Non-Cash Food Aid (BPNT) are:

- 1) Increase food security at the level of Beneficiary Families (KPM) as well as a mechanism for social protection and poverty reduction.
- 2) Increased non-cash transactions on the Non-Cash National Movement (GNNT) agenda.
- 3) Increased efficiency of distribution of social assistance.
- 4) Increased economic growth in the region, especially micro and small businesses in the field of trade.

Food assistance to poor families began in 1998 under the name of Special Market Operations (OPK). The year 2002 was replaced with the term rice for a prosperous family. In 2006 and 2007, 10 kg / family / month was set for one year. In 2013 the provision of food aid was unpaid. Beneficiary families can buy rice at a price of IDR 1,600 / kg.

There was a change in the distribution of food by the name of Non-Cash Food Assistance (BPNT) in 2017. They will receive the food equivalent to IDR 110,000 / month / family (Kuntjorowati, 2015).

Non-cash food aid distribution began in 2017 in 44 cities that have adequate access and facilities. Food aid is gradually extended to all cities and districts in accordance with the readiness of non-cash distribution facilities and infrastructure. In

Pematangsiantar City, the distribution of Non-Cash Food Assistance (BPNT) to 12,920 Beneficiary Families (KPM) only began on November 2018. This program is still being monitored significantly by the government, Ministry of Social Affairs, local government and other institutions involved in the distribution of BPNT because they are considered to be new programs (Jayaputra, 2017; Maharani, 2017).

2. Research Objectives

This study aims to see whether: 1) KPM meets the criteria as a recipient of BPNT, 2) BPNT influences the improvement of KPM household food security, 3) BPNT program influences the profits obtained by cooperating stalls / kiosks / shops.

2.1 Research Benefits

The benefits of this investigation are meant to produce reading material and additional literature for students and as a consideration for other researchers linked to this topic.

3. Research Methods

3.1 Research Materials and Methods

This research was conducted in Siantar Sitalasari District, Pematangsiantar City. This location was chosen because this area is one of the recipients of BPNT and an area that has never been studied by others.

Primary data is data obtained directly from respondents who received BPNT and stalls cooperating through interviews and observations to respondents through filling questionnaires with interview and recording techniques at the time the research took place (Arikounto, 1996; Sugiyono; 2013). Secondary data is data that is already available and obtained by researchers from statistical data such as the Central Statistics Agency and Pematangsiantar City Social Service.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Characteristics of Poor Households

Characteristics of poor households according to BPS in 2008 are carried out using access characteristics to basic needs that had 14 characteristics, namely;

- 1) floor area of residential buildings,
- 2) type of residential floor,
- 3) type of residential wall,
- 4) the facility for defecation,
- 5) household lighting sources,
- 6) drinking water sources,
- 7) fuel for cooking,
- 8) consumption of meat / chicken / milk / per week,

- 9) purchasing new clothes for each household member every year
- 10) frequency of eating in a day,
- 11) the ability to pay for treatment at a health center or a doctor,
- 12) employment of household heads,
- 13) the highest education of the head of the household,
- 14) ownership of movable or immovable assets.

To find out the characteristics of poor households in Siantar Sitalasari District, it can be seen from table 1 as follows:

Table 1: Classification of Characteristics of Poor Households

Score Class	Interval		Frequency	Average of Score Total
	Highest	Lowest		
Not poor	32	14	-	-
Poor	51	33	22	48,56
Extremely poor	70	52	26	54,62
Total			48	51,83

Source: Primary Data Processed (2019).

From the table above, it can be seen that the average score that meets the poor characteristics is 48.5 with a total of 22 KPM respondents and the average score that meets the very poor characteristics is 54.62 with a total of 26 KPM respondents.

The overall average score of 48 samples is 51.83. From the results obtained the average score ≥ 45 ($51.83 \geq 45$), it can be concluded that the recipient or KPM BPNT meets the characteristics of poor households and is entitled to get BPNT and on target based on characteristics in Siantar Sitalasari District, Pematangsiantar City.

4.2 Household Food Security KPM BPNT

Household food security is the ability to meet the food needs of all household members in number, quality, and variety according to local culture from time to time to live healthy. Based on the results of respondents' answers we can see household food security before and after becoming KPM BPNT from the following table:

From this table we can see that an increase in household food security before becoming KPM BPNT by 32.44% and after becoming KPM BPNT by 67.56% so it can be concluded that KPM BPNT household food security has increased by 35.12%.

Table 2: Percentage of Increase in Food Security Components

Indicators	Average Food Security Score		Percentage (%)
	Before	After	
Food Availability	7,21	14,21	45,67
Food Stability	6,83	12,88	49,62
Food Accessibility	5,13	13,38	55,30
Food Quality	6,67	13,33	49,41
Total	25,83	53,79	35,12

Source: Primary Data Processed (2019).

4.3 Benefits obtained by kiosk/ stalls/ shops/ as a BPNT Distribution agent

The role of Pematangsiantar City Social Service is very important in the distribution of Non-Cash Food Assistance (BPNT). The Social Service must ensure the distribution of BPNT to the Beneficiary Families (KPM). The social service must prepare well for the confirmation from Bansos Rastra to BPNT, especially from KPM data and stalls as distribution points.

The social service must proactively coordinate and synergize the related sub-districts and villages including Himbara (BRI) and the State Logistics Agency (Bulog) to BPNT so as to ensure the effectiveness of performance.

4.3.1 The profits obtained from the stall are from BPNT distribution

Table 3: Trader Benefits from BPNT distribution

Month	Redeem Value (Rp.)	Sales Value (Rp.)	Profit (Rp.)
November (2018)	14.280.000	14.960.000	680.000
December (2018)	25.935.000	27.170.000	1.235.000
January (2019)	30.450.000	31.900.000	1.450.000
February (2019)	22.575.000	23.650.000	1.075.000
March (2019)	25.725.000	26.950.000	1.225.000
April (2019)	35.700.000	37.400.000	1.700.000
May (2019)	36.855.000	38.610.000	1.755.000
June (2019)	24.675.000	25.850.000	1.175.000
Total	216.195.000	226.490.000	10.295.000
Average	27.024.375	28.311.250	1.286.875

Source: Primary data processed (2019).

The stall gets a sales value of Rp. 28,311,250 / month and a profit of Rp. 1,286,875 / month.

4.3.2 Benefits of BRI Bank

The profit obtained by the owner of the stall from Bank BRI is that in one transaction the machine gets a reward of Rp. 2,000, -. The intended benefit is not from the KPM rice purchase transaction, but if the agent makes payments to the National Logistics Agency or other shipments, then in one transaction the trader will receive a reward from BRI bank.

4.3.3 Advantages of other goods

Usually KPM BPNT who buy rice form the stalls also purchase other goods for their needs such as oil, sugar, soap, flour, and other items needed by KPM. As for the change in profits obtained by the stall after becoming a BPNT distributor agent can be seen from the following table:

Table 4: Benefits obtained from the stall after becoming an agent distributor of BPNT

No	Questions	Increased	Constant	Decline
1	Stall income after becoming a distributor of BPNT	√		
2	Sales of other goods after becoming a distributor of BPNT	√		
3	The number of buyers after becoming a distributor of BPNT	√		
4	Profits obtained from the sale of BPNT	√		
5	Profits obtained from the sale of other goods after becoming a distributor of BPNT	√		

Source: Primary Data Processed (2019).

From the table above we can see that the stall income, sales of other goods, number of buyers, profits from BPNT sales and other goods after the stalls collaborate and become BPNT distributor agents have increased for the stalls.

5. Conclusions and Suggestions

5.1 Conclusion

Based on the results of research conducted in Siantar Sitalasari District, Pematangsiantar City, the following conclusions are obtained:

- 1) Beneficiary Families (KPM) meet the criteria as recipients of Non-Cash Food Assistance (BPNT) with the results obtained an average score of ≥ 45 ($51.83 \geq 45$) in Siantar Sitalasari District, Pematangsiantar City.
- 2) Non-Cash Food Assistance (BPNT) affects the increase in household food security of Beneficiary Families (KPM) which can be seen from the increase in household food security before becoming KPM BPNT by 32.44% and after becoming KPM BPNT by 67.56% so it can be concluded that household food security of KPM BPNT has increased by 35.12%.
- 3) The Non-Cash Food Assistance Program (BPNT) affects the profits obtained by cooperating stalls / stalls / shops that we can see that both stalls earn a net income of Rp. 1,286,875 / month from rice alone and receive compensation from BRI banks. Rp.2,000, - / transaction and purchase of other goods in the Siantar Sitalasari District, Pematangsiantar City.

5.2 Suggestions

Suggestions that can be generated based on the results of research are as follows:

- 1) The government must continue to carry out such assistance policies or programs, carry out significant monitoring and verify the beneficiary community to find out whether or not they are eligible for assistance. The government must also increase or add other types of staples other than rice so people can choose what they need.
- 2) Beneficiary families should take rice every month so that the program will achieve its objectives, which is on time, on target, and a fixed amount and

through this assistance, it is expected that Beneficiary Families (KPM) use this assistance as well as possible.

- 3) Stall/ kiosks/ shops owners are expected to always provide good service for the beneficiary families.
- 4) To students, it is hoped that through this research we, as the society, must participate in supporting government programs like this.

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